

USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

The current article is about benefits and desirable outcomes of making use of unconventional teaching methods during an English lesson. Traditional methods of teaching were replaced by interactive ways in the late twentieth century, and this made a difference in both presentation of the new topic and consolidation of it. The whole class usually actively perform all the fascinating tasks given by the educator, even slow learners are involved in the lesson due to varying classroom activities the teacher and students have at the lesson. Lively lessons in which interactive ways of teaching are used may seem to make pupils noisy and spoiled, while they do a lot of good to language learners. That is they will increase students' knowledge, improve critical thinking, their self-confidence, break ice between the teacher and students, consolidate friendly relationships among schoolchildren,

Key words

interactive methods, teaching English, student-teacher interaction, a linguistic phenomenon, traditional teaching, a learner-centered approach, weak students, slow learners, high-achieving students, a learning process, a teaching process.

INTRODUCTION

With the growth of psychology in the late twentieth century, human mind was thoroughly studied and educationalists realized that in order to attract all the pupils' attention in the class, including high-achieving students and weak students educators need to use interactive methods, and this, they thought, would foster both teaching and learning process.

The term 'interactive' means making people work together, through which they have an impact on each other. Since they engage in a dialogue or a conversation in their target language, it requires an active role of students in the learning process [1, p. 159], and the main purpose of this form of education is to encourage pupils to forge a friendly and mutually supportive relationship [2, p. 7].

Role plays, brainstorming, case-study, presentations and discussions are the most widely spread teaching methods around the globe. They are believed to develop communicative skills, critical thinking and make students stay attentive

throughout the lesson [3, p. 30]. These learner-centered approaches are highly appropriate for language learners to acquire knowledge and skills [4, p. 9]

While educating younger generation teachers should have to be patient, because schoolchildren today are more attached to their smart phones, and educators ought to integrate the technology into the classroom by using teaching equipment such as an interactive whiteboard, which reminds students of their common distractions, and this can enable teachers to hold their students' attention. Moreover, some classroom activities are done with an interactive whiteboard, which involves student-teacher interaction

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three teaching methods are used in education: passive, active and interactive. The passive method assumes one actor - the teacher, who manages the course of the classes, and the students act as listeners. Often this form is practiced at lectures at the university. In the active method, the teacher and students interact with each other throughout the lesson. There is a third option - interactive which is used nowadays.

What is Interactive Learning? Interactive learning is originally a kind of active learning, which has grown into a separate method. Interaction occurs not only between the teacher and students, but also between groups or individual students. In another way, it is called "dialogue learning". Interactive forms help the teacher to captivate students with a lesson, motivate them for active participation, achievement of results and teamwork [6, p. 24]. The practice of involving learners in the educational process by encouraging them to bring their own experience and knowledge into the process, while also contributing to defining or organizing their learning. With this type of teaching approach, students learn in a different way - instead of being passive listeners to the lecture during the lesson, they are actively involved in the learning process by participating in activities, games, discussions, solving mysteries, storytelling, and so on [5, p. 50].

Principles Interactive learning means:

- activities and relationships, thanks to which both the teacher and the students are involved in the process and are looking for solutions;
- equality in communication, which helps to openly discuss possible outcomes;
- experiments, creative approach

Learning media are the objects that the teacher uses to teach and present materials. The basis of interactive learning is visualization, since most part of the information is perceived by the child with the help of vision.

Among them are often distinguished:

-interactive whiteboards;

-interactive set-top boxes, projectors, displays;

-robotics and LEGO constructors;

-interactive table wireless tablet;

-document camera - a device under which a textbook is placed and its image is projected onto a computer and an interactive whiteboard;

-an interactive sandbox, which, in addition to sand, has a projector and software that creates an additional reality;

-mobile planetarium -a building specially equipped to show images of the stars in the sky and other objects in space on a curved ceiling;

-computers and office equipment

Forms of interactive learning.

Forms of learning are types of activities. Here, the teacher needs more activity and creativity than with other options for conducting lessons[10, p. 87]. At the same time, when preparing for each specific topic or subject, you can use different forms or a combination of them:

-Master classes are the transfer of practical experience from the teacher to the students;

-Interactive webinars are a traditional lecture along with a discussion, projects ,slides or films;

-Cases are a solution to a specific situation;

-Voting, polls-a discussion during which students are actively involved in the search for truth, openly share their opinions and learn to argue their point of view;

-Brainstorming is the joint generation of ideas and the search for non-standard creative solutions;

-Projects - independent work on the task;

-Trainings - a joint search for a solution to a problem, followed by a discussion;

-"Microphone"- the statement of one student on the problem posed, the rest do not comment;

-"Brownian motion" is a chaotic movement around the class in search of a solution;

-Debates are justified and reasoned statements of two sides.

Business games - playing situations;

-"Aquarium" is a kind of business games where participants who were not involved in the process comment on what is happening;

-Rotational trios - work in a group of three people, in which the composition changes with each next task;

-Couples and small groups - work with two or more participants.

Benefits for pupils:

-independence, as you need to look for information in different sources;

-developed communication skills for the exchange of experience;

-critical thinking;

-creative skills;

-mental health, as the method helps to relieve increased mental and academic stress;

-easy assimilation of the material;

-expanded cognitive possibilities [7, p. 96].

Difficulties for the teacher:

-maintaining a balance between play and learning;

-adaptation of the method to the characteristics of the character and behavior of children;

-high level of organizational skills;

-time spent on learning a new method;

-the fight against anxiety and discomfort of children with the introduction of a new format;

-one topic is more time-consuming to study compared to passive and active methods;

-energy consumption.

Disadvantages of the method:

-a small number of methodological developments;

-insufficient qualification of teachers;

-high financial costs for equipment.

Interactive learning helps to make the lessons interesting, gives the child the opportunity to become an active participant in the learning process, share their opinions and experiences, learn to interact with the team and make independent decisions[8, p. 67].

Purpose of interactive learning:

-develop communication skills;

-create comfortable conditions and a favorable emotional environment for all participants in the lesson;

-develop teamwork skills and the ability to express their opinions;

-arouse interest in learning and intrinsic motivation;

-unleash creativity.

The same old style of teaching is no longer interesting as it keeps the students in the classroom often bored. Whereas students during the lecture style often do that lose interest [11, p. 76]. Instead, they are interested in interactive teaching styles to create an atmosphere of attention and participation to them sympathetic, pleasant and interesting. Interactive teaching methods make the classes exciting and fill them with fun [9, p. 134]. As you know, storytelling is not teaching and not listening, not learning.

The methods used to educate children may have similarities with the past, but they have each other changed overall as technology has advanced and room for more made innovations. Nowadays, the average student day can in it consist of sitting at a desk and listening to the teacher but it is very inclusive probably also things like hands-on practice game-based learning and digital inventions. One could argue that technology has made education more engaging than ever has become. Classrooms have taken on a new life [12, p 45]. Interactive learning has become the new standard to engage generations to teach future. It is about providing students with a comprehensive to offer experience that aims to not just theoretical level, but also give them examples and practical experience, give to reinforce the knowledge they absorb. The main idea behind this teaching approach is to ensure that students understand information completely instead of just memorizing it and repeat. Interactive learning has many benefits, extending beyond a large one range of skills and educational milestones [15, p. 66].

Interactive teaching styles should focus on:

- encourage students participation;
- present such questions that will generate stimulating answers, discussions, and expect practical experience;
- use teaching aids that urge answers and capture the attention of students;
- Set up a workgroup environment;
- Involve yourself as well as the student.

Great teachers are nimble, observant, and responsive, always keeping an open mind about how to best engage their students and get them excited about learning—and that means considering trying out different interactive teaching styles in the classroom[14, p. 90].

Interactive teaching styles are designed around a simple principle: without practical application, students often fail to comprehend the depths of the study material. Interactive teaching is also beneficial for you as the teacher in a number of ways, including:

Measurable student accomplishments: Teachers making use of interactive teaching styles are better equipped to assess how well students master a given subject material.

Flexibility in teaching: Applying training methods that involve two-way communications will enable you to make quick adjustments in processes and approaches.

Practice makes perfect: Interactive instruction enhances the learning process.

Student motivation: Two-way teaching dispels student passivity, and when more students are engaged, you'll have much more fun too.

Interactive learning is an educational one approach that integrates social networking and urban computing into the design and conducting courses included Interactive learning has evolved from the hyper-growth in the use of digital technology and virtual communication, especially by students. The use of digital media in education led to an increasing use of and dependence on interactive learning, which in turn revolutionized the basic educational process has led. Students and teachers increasingly rely on each other accessing knowledge sources and sharing their information, expanding the general scope of the educational process, which includes not only teaching, but the expansion of knowledge. The role change from the keeper of knowledge to the promoter of learning represents a challenge and an opportunity for educators to how their students learn to change fundamentally. The boundaries between teachers and students have less importance in interactive learning. To be effective, educational institutions need computers and related technology as an integral part of the student. In other words Technology must be viewed as a cognitive tool. The core concept of distance learning consists in the real world becoming the learning environment, in this environment, the purpose of the instructor is to help facilitate that assumption of knowledge through real and virtual learning experiences. Historically, one of the barriers to distance learning has been the lack of personal contact [13, p. 78]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Critical thinking is an intellectual system formed in a person that provides purposeful perception, awareness, assessment of significance, analysis of facts for a complete understanding of the topic. These are the main foundations of critical thinking.

Critical thinking is an important skill that helps you analyze information, draw conclusions, form your own opinion on any issue and act in accordance with it. Critical thinking helps to successfully cope with educational and work tasks, make decisions and navigate the flow of information. To develop critical thinking,

strive to expand your horizons and learn more about different objects and phenomena, learn to ask questions, analyze the text, come up with different scenarios. Games, puzzles, and other exercises can help you develop your reasoning, focus, and inventiveness. The more knowledge, the easier it is to compare and analyze. Before critically assessing the problem, it must be considered from all sides, to see the situation in the context of other events, to follow its development over time.

Learn to ask questions. Curiosity and a thirst for knowledge are the basis of critical thinking; in order to satisfy this thirst, it is necessary to be able to formulate questions correctly. Practice asking questions on a variety of topics. When studying any issue, be interested in all aspects, consider the problem from different angles and clarify the details.

Analyze text. Analyze the information to determine its reliability and understand it well enough to draw further conclusions. This is one of the most important aspects of critical thinking.

Think of different scenarios. Learn to predict the consequences of your actions in any life situation. When making a decision, write down on paper all the likely consequences, evaluate each of them, think about how to minimize the risk of failure or possible negative consequences [12, p 66]

The process usually includes steps such as gathering information, asking thoughtful questions, and exploring possible solutions. Perfected critical thinking skills allow you to correctly understand the circumstances, correctly resolve issues, and reasonably get out of controversial situations. They help to find the most optimal course of action based on all available facts, analyzed information.

The development of critical thinking in adults is a necessary step to achieve success in a career and business [10, p. 99]. Techniques for applying critical thinking in the professional field make it possible to quickly process and systematize data to identify problems and develop effective solutions. It is important to develop in the classroom the thinking abilities of children studying in elementary school, high school, and higher educational institutions. A high level of intelligence contributes to academic achievement, memorization of information. The ability of students and adults to competently use cognitive potential prevents mental exhaustion, mental overload. A useful idea is to reflect on the existing intellectual abilities, study the theory, set a realistic goal, practice critical thinking techniques, for example, play erudite games.

Guess the Continuation.

This game simultaneously develops both critical and creative thinking. Take any story. Let's say Little Red Riding Hood. Stop at the moment where the girl comes to her grandmother. The learner will need to come up with their own continuation of the story. Ask him leading questions, ask why, in his opinion, the fairy tale should end this way. The game will be even more interesting if pupil knows the original ending. Exercises will also allow you to better understand the inner world of your children find common topics for discussion. You will both learn and grow intellectually with your children.

Create your own story.

This activity not only improves pupil's critical thinking but also develops their creative writing. Each participant has different versions of given pictures.

A role-playing game is an educational or entertaining game in which the participant acts out his role and, together with other players, creates some kind of imaginary situation.

Pictures-riddles.

One leader is selected from a group of children, the rest sit on chairs, they must guess. The teacher has a large box in which there are small pictures depicting various objects. The volunteer approaches the teacher and takes one of the pictures. Without showing it to the other children, he describes the object drawn on it. Children offer their own various versions. The next volunteer is the one who first guessed the correct answer

Hat The good old game, which is a success at adult parties. It's more fun to play with a group, but if you're playing with two, have someone else write the words on pieces of paper and fold them into a hat. The player draws a card and with the help of associations, descriptions of properties, etc. explains what happened to him. You must guess.

Finish the sentence.

Think of different situations and invite the child to complete the phrase. This exercise forces you to find options for the development of events, causal relationships.

Method of "Information folding" (sinkwine).

Sinkwine is a specific poem, without rhyme, consisting of five lines, each of which carries specific information about the described object or phenomenon. In its content, it is the answer to five questions in your own words. In the process of compiling a syncwine, the theme is understood.

The procedure and rules for compiling a syncwine, line by line:

-The title of the topic, in one word (noun):summer

-Describing a topic with two adjectives: hot bright

-Description of the action within the topic, in three words: swim,play,chill

-Describing the relationship to the topic in four words: Summer is the best season of the year

-A synonym that repeats the essence of the topic: holiday

<<Information deployment>> method (cluster).

The breakdown of the topic into clusters is a pedagogical strategy aimed at developing the variability of thinking and the ability to establish connections in the concept (event or phenomenon) being studied, the ability to think openly and freely on a specific topic.

The sequence and rules for compiling a cluster:In the center of the sheet of paper where the cluster is made, a keyword or sentence is written.Around the central word, several words or sentences related to the theme.Making connections between ideas and concepts.Writing as many variations of ideas on a topic as possible

Discussion.

Before beginning the discussion, participants in this interactive method must read the relevant teaching materials. The students may begin discussion once they have mastered the lexico-grammatical material related to the topic. By providing support for the learners' statements, this approach enables them to consistently and logically express their ideas. Because each member of the group is given the opportunity to speak up and participate in the discussion, the activity of the students who are working in small groups here is improved. The following are the different ways to structure group work: A theme is chosen (chosen); B students must have mastered the chosen problem; C groups are formed; D the teacher gives instructions and announces the time; E the teacher controls the activity of the students and, if necessary, helps and stimulates them. f) One representative from each group makes a presentation at the conclusion of the discussion [7, p. 96].

Brainstorming.

It is a method for coming up with fresh ideas about a subject. These teaching techniques encourage learners to use their creativity to solve issues and express concepts in a variety of ways. Here, various solutions to the problem are typically provided. When brainstorming, quantity is more important than quality. The teacher should be open-minded and listen to all students' opinions. Instead of doing this, he encourages the students to offer as many possible solutions to the problem. Lack of criticism fosters an environment where students may express their thoughts freely, which naturally motivates them. All of the expressed

utterances are recorded and then examined at the conclusion of the brainstorming process.

Role playing.

Innovative teaching techniques often include role-playing exercises. The effectiveness of instruction is improved by them. By having a favorable impact on students' inner activity, role acting engages students in active learning. Because of this, collaborative work can flourish. Such an environment fosters their motivation and inner potential while also assisting in the development of practical abilities and habits. Skills like originality, ingenuity, getting out of tight spots, and self-management are developed and enhanced during role-playing. As some real-life situations are recreated here for instruction, role playing includes social as well as educational goals.

The following guidelines should be followed by a teacher when using the role-playing approach to teach a foreign language:

-Establishing a friendly atmosphere among the participants in the play; -

Learners should feel free to express themselves, as this will enable them to play their roles flawlessly

-establishing beneficial settings for learning and employing pros;

-taking into account the unique characteristics of the students

CONCLUSION

The scheme of interactive teaching methods is based on the schemes of interaction "teacher-students" and "student-student". These schemes imply that not only the teacher, but also the students themselves are involved in the learning process through interaction with each other. The interaction "student - student" contributes to the increase of educational motivation, the manifestation of initiative in the learning process.

Critical thinking, able to come up with new ideas and see new possibilities, is essential in problem solving. It helps to successfully cope with educational and work tasks, make decisions and navigate the flow of information. To develop critical thinking, strive to expand your horizons and learn more about different objects and phenomena, learn to ask questions, analyze the text, come up with different scenarios.

Speech activity is an active, purposeful, mediated by the language system and conditioned by the situation of communication, the process of transmitting or receiving a message, i.e. production and reception process. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, it is customary to distinguish between productive and receptive types of speech activity. Productive types of speech activity are processes

associated with the generation of speech [12, p. 56]. These include speaking (i.e., the generation of oral speech) and writing (i.e., the generation of written speech). Receptive types of speech activity are processes associated with the perception of speech. These include listening (i.e., perception of oral speech) and reading (i.e., perception of written speech).

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